

EFFECT OF DEGASSING CONDITIONS AND SiCp TYPE ON THE PROPERTIES OF
A P/M 2014 MMC

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ABSTRACT

Al 2014 alloy and SiC particulates were used to produce MMCs of 2.4, 9.3 and 15_v% SiCp through a sequence of mixing, canning, degassing and hot extrusion steps. Two different types of SiCp and three different degassing temperatures were used. The extrusions were carried out at 300°C using an extrusion ratio of 16:1. The microstructures and properties of the as extruded and as T₆ heat treated material were determined and compared with the properties of spray co-deposited MMC (9.3_v% SiCp) supplied for this purpose and similarly processed.

Degassing temperature was found not to have a significant effect on the final properties. The most relevant processing parameter was related to the efficiency of powder mixing which is determined by the relative powder size distributions and volume fractions.

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that the degassing step used in the P/M extrusion processing route for aluminium alloy powder is critical in obtaining improved final properties (1). A similar route can be used for P/M MMC processing, the final properties obtained for equivalent 2014/SiCp composites being quite different when a degassing treatment is applied (2) or not (3). On the other hand, a recently described spray co-deposition process which corresponds to a much simplified processing route, has no degassing involved and gives rise to an attractive combination of properties (4).

It was therefore considered of interest to assess the possible effect of different degassing temperatures on MMCs obtained through the P/M route, as well as comparing composites of similar volume % of reinforcement particles obtained by the P/M and the spray co-deposition routes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Al 2014 argon gas atomized powder* of wt % composition 4.43 Cu, 0.92 Si, 0.67 Mn, 0.45 Mg, 0.021 Zn, Cr << 0.005, Ti < 0.05 and two types of untreated SiC particulate labelled (A)* and (B)** have been used. The 2014 powder was of spherical shape and both SiC of predominantly angular shape. Their particle size distribution was determined using a laser based method in a CILAS 715 instrument, the median size being 78 μm, 12 μm and 4 μm respectively for 2014, SiC (A) and SiC (B) (Fig. 1).

Composite mixtures of 9.3_v% SiC (A), 15_v% SiC (A) and 15_v% SiC (B) were prepared by dry blending in a Turbula tumbler, for about 3 hours. Time of blending for each mixture was selected as corresponding to the minimum variance of the Al wt %, in preliminary blending experiments. These mixtures as well as a 2.4_v% SiC (A) one were

* ALCAN International, Banbury, England

** STRUERS, Copenhagen, Denmark

Fig. 1 Cumulative size distributions of 2014 and SiC particulate

poured and tapped into cans to an apparent density of around 65% of the theoretical density. Cans were of a similar design to those described previously (5), and made of 6082 aluminium alloy, with an interior lead angle of 90° and wall thickness of 10 mm.

Degassing was carried out at 350°C , 400°C and 500°C for four hours, at around 10^{-2} Pa, after which the cans were sealed and air cooled. Typical pressure change during the heating up to the degassing temperature (~ 3 hours) showed a continuous release of presumably H_2O vapour between 100°C and 300°C and another peak of pressure centered at around 350°C (6).

Extrusion of the canned powder mixtures and of an uncanned spray co-deposited 9.3% SiC (A) composite billet supplied by Alcan (both of 73 mm diameter) was carried out in a vertical press of 10 MN capacity. The container of 76 mm bore diameter was preheated to approximately 300°C . Lubrication with graphite/molybdenum disulphide grease was used in the container bore and the die. Canned and billet composites were reheated for 2 hours in an air circulating furnace at a set temperature of 300°C and extruded to round bar at an extrusion ratio of 16:1 with a ram speed of approximately 5 mm sec^{-1} . Extruded bars were allowed to cool naturally.

Optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) examination was carried out on polished samples of the as extruded rods. Samples of each rod were given the standard T_6 heat treatment for the 2014 wrought alloy (502°C solution treatment, water quenching, 160°C ageing for 18 hours) and were again examined by optical and scanning electron microscopy. Brinell hardness and tensile tests were performed on heat treated material. The tensile tests were carried out in a universal testing machine at a constant cross-head speed of $3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm sec}^{-1}$, on specimens of 6.4 mm diameter and 32.0 mm gauge length. Compact notched specimens from some as extruded and as heat treated composites were machined for mass spectrometry study of fractures, as described elsewhere (6). Fracture surfaces of these specimens as well as of tension test specimens were examined by SEM. Densities were determined by a picnometer method on $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}$ cylinders of T_6 treated material.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The P/M composites showed the same characteristic shape of extrusion pressure-distance curves as described previously for the extrusion of 7075 powders (5). No systematic differences were found either for different volume fractions, type of SiC or degassing treatment. A typical curve, showing clearly a long upset distance for consolidation [1-2], breakthrough of the can [2] followed by that for the powder [3] and start of back end defect [4] is presented in Fig. 2. The curve corresponding to the uncanned spray co-deposited billet shows a short upset distance indicative of an approximately 100% dense starting material. The peak pressure for the composite breakthrough is 30% higher than for the canned extrusion but falls down quickly to an identical level of steady state pressure. All extrudates had satisfactory surface finish, including the

uncanned co-deposited composite. In every case no deterioration of the die was observed.

Fig. 2 Typical extrusion pressure-distance curves

All the microstructures show a reasonably homogeneous distribution of the SiC particles on transverse sections and some banding in the extrusion direction on longitudinal sections. Except for the slight coarsening of the matrix precipitates, no systematic effect of the increase in degassing temperature was found. The spray co-deposited composite shows coarser precipitates than the P/M composites but still smaller than those expected for a cast material (4); some of those precipitates were found to follow closely the contour of the SiC particles suggesting heterogeneous precipitation and growth on these particles.

Fig. 3 shows typical microstructures of longitudinal sections of the heat treated extrudates where the extent of heterogeneities in the 15_v% SiC composite is clearly visible, particularly for SiC (B) (Fig. 3 (e)). Voids associated with SiC clusters are frequently found in the 15_v% SiC composite, particularly for the fine grained SiC (B). The density determined for the 2.4_v% SiC material (see Table 1) is less than expected from the densities of the two constituents, although almost no interparticle voids were detected. However the 2014 aluminium particles had internal porosity (6) and assuming about 1% of porosity the difference in densities can be accounted for. Evidence from mass spectrometry shows that some argon is released from fresh fracture surfaces (6), indicating that at least some pores are filled with argon and therefore were not closed by extrusion. The 9.3_v% SiC composites have a higher density, compatible with the higher SiC content and the same aluminium particles porosity. The lower densities of the 15_v% SiC composites suggest at least 3.5% additional cavities for the SiC (B) and 2% for SiC (A) type, which are consistent with the microstructural observations.

Fracture in the mass spectrometry tested specimen shows the expected orientation for both 9.3_v% SiC materials (Fig. 4 (b)) whereas both 15_v% SiC materials fractured along the extrusion direction (Fig. 4 (c)). The appearance of the fracture surfaces of Figs. 5 (a) and (b) supports these observations which indicate poor transverse toughness for the 15_v% SiC composites, arising from the banding of SiC and consequent

Fig. 3 Optical microstructures of longitudinal sections of extruded composites: (a) 2.4% SiC (A); (b) 9.3% SiC (A); (c) 9.3% SiC (A) co-deposited; (d) 15% SiC (A); (e) 15% SiC (B)

Fig. 4 Schematic diagram of: (a) notched specimen dimensions for mass spectrometry of fractures; (b) fracture orientation of 9.3% SiC composites; (c) fracture orientation of 15% SiC composites

elongated cavities in the extrusion direction.

Tensile properties are compared with those expected for the 2014 matrix in Table 1. Results for the 350, 400 and 500°C degassing temperatures were closely reproducible, with no systematic trend detected. Proof stresses fell within an interval of $\pm 1\%$ except for the 15% SiC (B) where it was $\pm 3\%$. Ductility was somewhat more scattered but again with no systematic variation. Therefore only the mean properties for each material are shown in the table.

Table 1 Properties of experimental composites

% SiC	Density ρ (g/cm ³)	Proof stress R _{0.2} (MPa)	Elongation (%)
0*	2.80	414	13.0
2.4 (A)	2.77	429	11.6
9.3 (A)	2.81	466	4.1
9.3 (A), spray co-deposited)	2.82	468	4.1
15 (A)	2.78	457	1.3
15 (B)	2.74	411	0.8

* data from reference 7

Fracture appearance of typical 15% SiC tensile specimens is shown in Figs. 5 (c) and (d). Fractures are transverse to the extrusion direction and show the same characteristics as

Fig. 5 Scanning electron micrographs of fracture surfaces of: (a) notched specimen of 9.3% SiC co-deposited composite; (b) notched specimen of 15% SiC (A) composite; (c), (d) tensile specimens of 15% SiC (A) composites

the lower SiC volume fraction material in Fig. 5 (a). Most SiC particles appear intact suggesting that debonding between the ceramic and the matrix occurs during fracture. However some SiC particles are fractured and occasionally show adherent matrix, indicating a good level of interface bonding (Fig. 5 (d)). The intervening 2014 matrix shows dimple intragranular ductile fracture rather than intergranular separation. Further evidence of fracture through the aluminium alloy particles is the release of entrapped argon (6). For all the degassing treatments given, the nature of the fractures shows that the bonding between the 2014 aluminium particles is satisfactory after extrusion at a 16:1 extrusion ratio. Additional extrusions at a 10:1 extrusion ratio with 15_v% SiC (A) and 15_v% SiC (B) have shown inadequate bonding and virtually near zero ductility. The ductility depends on the specific area of SiC/2014 interfaces (c.f. 0, 2.4 and 9.3%) as well as on the area fraction of voids present (c.f. 9.3%, 15% (A) and 15% (B)). The proof stress increases with increasing volume fraction of SiC but is decreased in the 15_v% SiC composites and particularly in 15_v% SiC (B) due to the presence of voids.

CONCLUSIONS

1. With 9.3_v% SiC the two process routes for 2014/SiCp fabrication (extrusion of canned and degassed powder mixtures and of spray co-deposited billet) give essentially the same microstructure and mechanical properties.
2. With the fairly coarse Al particle distribution used in the present work, the best properties are obtained at 9.3_v% SiC because higher ceramic content causes clustering of the SiC particles and consequently creates interparticle voids within the ceramic clusters.
3. Fracture generally occurs, for the 9.3_v% SiC materials, by a ductile transgranular mode in the 2014 matrix, with the creation and coalescence of voids around precipitates and SiC particles and ultimate formation of a dimpled fracture surface.
4. Degassing at temperatures from 350°C to 500°C gives no significant effect on properties after extrusion at 300°C with a 16:1 extrusion ratio.

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